

ALG-SDE: Developing an Arduino-Based System for Automated Algae Detection and Algaecide Treatment

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ABSTRACT

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) present ecological and public health threats in freshwater systems in the Philippines. Despite attempts of traditional mitigation techniques, they are limited by manual monitoring and treatment delays. Which is why there is a need for automated systems that provide real-time intervention. This study developed and evaluated ALG-SDE, an Arduino-based prototype using pH, temperature, and turbidity sensors to detect and respond to algae conditions via algaecide dispensing. Results showed statistically significant reductions in pH ($t = 39.28$, $p = 0.00065$) and turbidity ($t = 9.45$, $p = 0.011$), with a strong inverse correlation ($r = -0.87$) between the two. Chi-square tests confirmed threshold-based activation inconsistencies ($p = 0.038$), suggesting sensor recalibration is needed. In conclusion, the system effectively alters algae-conducive conditions but requires improved reliability in real-time activation as well as mobility. Further iterations should focus on enhanced sensor accuracy, mobility features, and broader aquatic applicability.

KEYWORDS: Algal blooms, Algae, Algae Growth, Algaecide, pH, Turbidity, Temperature, Arduino

INTRODUCTION

There has been a serious threat to freshwater ecosystems, impacting aquatic life and human health; Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) are the main reason behind events like Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning and widespread fish kills, often referred to as "red tides." Historical cases, such as the devastating bloom in Maqueda Bay, Philippines, highlight the long-standing nature of this issue, which has resulted in numerous health problems and fatalities linked to contaminated shellfish. Despite various mitigation strategies—such as mechanical removal and nutrient reduction—there is a pressing need for more effective approaches that integrate advanced technology. This study aims to evaluate the accuracy and the ability of the Arduino-Based System to function on its own to mitigate potential HABs, while also examining key environmental factors like pH, temperature, and turbidity. Utilizing an Arduino-based automated algaecide dispensing system could enhance the management of HABs, providing a scalable solution to protect both aquatic ecosystems and public health from their detrimental effects.

Background of the Study

While human poisonings from Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning and Ciguatera Fish Poisoning have been documented, the widespread occurrence of Fish Kill Events, often referred to as "red tides" due to the water's discoloration, highlights the broader ecological consequences of HABs (Azanza et al., 2024). Massive algal blooms have also been recorded over time in multiple areas of the Philippines, one of the oldest being in Maqueda Bay in western Samar in 1983, highlighted the first historically damaging algal bloom and was said to have happened as early as 1908. In the case of Maqueda Bay which resulted from

Pyrodinium bahamense it resulted in 278 PSP cases and 21 fatalities from eating affected shellfish. Small bays where shellfish are farmed, are where algal bloom epidemics occur in the Philippines (Yñiguez et al., 2020). Aside from its harmful effects on aquaculture, it also poses a huge threat to humans, as a study in Puerto Princesa Bay investigated the relationship between informal settlements and water quality (Garcellano et al., 2022). The findings revealed the presence of harmful algal blooms (HABs) in waters near these settlements. These occurrences may not happen every day, but it is a serious case when it does.

Problem Statement:

This study will investigate the issues on Algae proliferation by examining the following:

1. What are the thresholds that indicate the possibility of algal blooms?
 - a. pH level
 - b. Temperature
 - c. Turbidity
2. What are the algae levels before and after treatment?
3. Did the Sensor-Based Algae Detection System effectively trigger algaecide release, staying within the predefined threshold?
4. Is there a significant difference in algae level according to the Arduino-Based Algaecide System (between initial and final measurements)?

H_a = There is a significant difference in the overall water quality between the pre-treatment and the post-treatment in the treatment group.

Significance

This research addresses the significant threat of harmful algal blooms (HABs) to aquatic ecosystems and human health by developing an Arduino-based system for detection and mitigation. Integrating sensors for key environmental parameters, pH (Yu et al., 2022), temperature (Singh & Singh, 2015), and turbidity (Ferrando et al., 2015), the system will monitor conditions conducive to HAB formation. Along with an automated algaecide dispensing mechanism, this approach offers several advantages as to improved efficiency through real-time monitoring and response, reduced costs compared to manual methods, scalability for deployment in various freshwater bodies, and significant contributions to protecting aquatic ecosystems and public health by minimizing HAB proliferation and exposure to harmful algal toxins.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Existing studies have examined aeration and remote monitoring for HAB mitigation. (Marcuello et al., 2020) developed a solar-powered compressor with an Arduino Uno-based monitoring system using Bluetooth to increase dissolved oxygen levels, countering algal growth. (Boddula et al., 2017) utilized Raspberry Pi and Arduino platforms for remote HAB detection based on cyanobacteria and chlorophyll levels, integrating suppression agents. These approaches demonstrate the potential for low-cost, technology-driven HAB management solutions. Building on this, the current study uses affordable Arduino sensors to monitor pH, temperature, and turbidity,

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study uses a quantitative experimental design and prototyping to develop an Arduino-based automated algaecide treatment system. It examines whether sensor-based detection of turbidity, pH, and temperature can effectively trigger algaecide dispensing by comparing control (no algaecide) and treatment groups (algaecide applied). Algae growth is measured through turbidity (NTU), with consistent conditions ensuring the algaecide's impact is isolated. The prototype's performance is evaluated to explore its

feasibility and identify areas for improvement in automated algae management (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019; Koskinen & Frens, 2017).

Materials and Components

In this study, an Arduino Uno R3 board was utilized as the central processing unit. A pH sensor, specifically the Arduino Gravity Analog model, was employed to measure the acidity or alkalinity of the solution. A temperature sensor was integrated to monitor the water temperature, providing critical data for assessing water quality. A turbidity sensor was included to evaluate the clarity of the water, which is essential for understanding its cleanliness and potential contamination levels. A water pump was also incorporated into the system to release algaecide automatically once specific thresholds for pH, temperature, or turbidity were exceeded. To facilitate connections between the components, a breadboard was used, along with connecting wires. The Arduino IDE, the integrated development environment for Arduino, was used to program the board. Additionally, relevant Arduino libraries were incorporated to enhance the functionality of the setup.

Prototype Design

Figure 1. Prototype Design

The prototype design for ALG-SDE involves a compact and portable unit. The core components, including the Arduino microcontroller, sensors (pH, turbidity, and temperature), and algaecide cartridge, were housed within a water-resistant plastic casing. This casing was further insulated with layers of Styrofoam tubes for buoyancy and to enhance environmental stability. This design facilitated direct water contact with the sensors for accurate data collection while ensuring the integrity of the internal components.

Prototyping Tools and Equipment

Developing and testing the Arduino-based algaecide treatment system required specialized equipment and common tools. A flathead screwdriver secured components, while a multimeter ensured proper voltage and circuit functionality for reliable sensor readings and algaecide dispensing. A laptop facilitated coding, programming, and uploading control software, managing sensor data, treatment thresholds, and pump activation. It also logged and stored sensor data for analysis. Standardized protocols, algae cultures, and controlled growth environments ensured experimental reliability and consistency.

Assembly Process

Figure 2. Assembly process

Assembling the ALG-SDE required a hands-on approach with careful planning. The researchers gathered all necessary components—Arduino UNO R3, sensors, LCD, and water pump—ensuring nothing was missing. They first connected everything through the breadboard and Arduino Uno R3, wiring power and data connections to enable sensor processing, LCD display, and system control, while also hooking up the water pump. After placing the components in their designated containers, they conducted a trial test, identified and corrected errors, and finalized the setup for data collection.

Wiring and Schematic Diagram

Figure 3. Schematic Diagram

To properly assemble and wire ALG-SDE, the researchers designed a schematic diagram to identify and determine where each component connects in the prototype's assembly. The diagram helps clear confusion when assembling ALG-SDE.

Figure 4. Wiring Diagram

A wiring diagram was designed to show how the prototype works and as a way for manufacturers to copy and wire the components of the prototype.

Programming Logic

Figure 5. Programming Logic

To detect and treat harmful algal blooms with ALG-SDE, start by turning the Arduino board on. Next is to let it calibrate its system, then wait for it to gather data. Afterward, check the LCD screen, if there's an alert; If yes, the water pump will release algicide to manage the environment. If not, the code will loop.

Testing Procedures

The pH sensor measures water acidity, a key indicator of algae presence. The thermometer sensor records water temperature, which influences algal bloom growth, though it is a weaker indicator. The turbidimeter, the primary sensor for algae detection, measures water cloudiness in Nephelometric Turbidity

Units (NTU), using a four-level chart: "Fairly Turbid" (15-25 NTU), "Rather Turbid" (25-35 NTU), "Turbid" (35-50 NTU), and "Very Turbid" (50+ NTU). Even lower turbidity may signal algae growth. Sensor data will be recorded in a spreadsheet and reviewed by a professional statistician for accuracy.

Specimen Collection

The water used for testing was collected from a fish pond located in Alabang West Parade. During the initial attempt, the collected sample became unviable due to prolonged travel time in an airtight container over the weekend, which likely caused oxygen depletion. In the second attempt, although improvements were made, the sample again became unviable due to insufficient nutrients to sustain the algae. Finally, on the third and successful attempt, 200 mL of pond water was collected and used for testing under optimized conditions.

Data Collection

Researchers employed the three aforementioned sensors to analyze samples divided into three cups for the threshold collection. Initially, the sensors were used to test the samples before manually adding the algacide. Following this, the sensors were used again to assess whether the algacide had effectively eliminated the algae. The thresholds were determined by recording the pH, temperature, and turbidity levels and averaging these values across all samples. These averaged thresholds would then be integrated into the prototype.

Additional sample water was divided into three cups for the water pump testing, while a fourth cup contained normal water. The water pump was designed to release algacide into the water once the sensors detected the previously recorded thresholds. The researchers conducted three trials using the algae-infested water and one trial using the normal water, with each trial involving 10 dips. In the algae water trials, it was expected that the water pump would release algacide all 10 times, as the water should already be at or above the threshold levels. In contrast, during the normal water trial, it was anticipated that the pump would not release algacide, since the normal water should not reach any of the thresholds. The researchers calibrated the Analog Turbidity Sensor Module with the method of placing it into two samples. One cloudy and one clear, then based the data on the chart by Akhmad et al. (2015).

Table 1. Turbidity Chart

No	Turbidity level	TSM (NTU)
1	Fairly turbid	15 – 25
2	Rather turbid	25 – 35
3	Turbid	35 – 50
4	Very turbid	> 50

The sensor calibration for pH levels was done by placing it in neutral water, to match the data provided in the chart by The University of Waikato Te Whare Wānanga o Waikato (2021).

Figure 6. pH meter Calibration Chart

The DS18B20 temperature sensor was calibrated using three distinct temperature samples: boiling water, lukewarm water, and ice-cold water. Then compared and re-adjusted based on the instructions and data provided by (Instructables, 2018)

Validation of Testing and Data Collection

The study underwent rigorous validation under the supervision of Mr. Lemuel Ramos, the Research and Prototype teacher, who provided technical guidance on both the paper and the prototype. External consultant, Mr. Davidson Escalona, contributed coding expertise on the prototype. Finally, Mr. Joshua Buarao provided the utmost guidance involving his biology expertise, assisting in terms of maximizing the potential of an algae bloom prevention system.

Statistical Treatment

The Paired T-test was used to analyze differences in algae levels before and after treatment as it compares two related datasets, the initial and final turbidity measurements, while accounting for variability within each culture. The Chi-square test determined whether the Algae Prevention System triggered correctly based on the coded threshold since it assesses deviations from expected outcomes. ANOVA was used to compare pH, temperature, and turbidity levels across multiple groups to identify significant differences. The prototype's effectiveness was evaluated by examining final algae levels and verifying proper threshold activation.

Limitations

The prototype, while demonstrating the feasibility of automated algae management, is a simplified model. Although it integrates pH, turbidity, and temperature sensors for a more comprehensive view of water quality, these localized readings may not represent larger, more complex aquatic environments. The Arduino Uno R3, while suitable for this initial study, has limited processing power and memory, which could be a constraint in more complex deployments. Finally, the prototype can only cover so much surface area of the body of water, giving it very limited areas to test the water unless with human intervention.

Ethical and Risk Considerations

This research upheld strict ethical standards, ensuring honesty, integrity, and environmental responsibility. Water samples from Alabang, Muntinlupa, were maintained under controlled conditions for cyanobacteria growth until testing. After automated bloom detection by the Arduino system, treatments were applied, and data were collected. All instruments and methods were expert-approved for reliability, with data integrity strictly maintained. No animals or marine life were harmed, reflecting a commitment to conservation. Findings will be publicly accessible to support future research and awareness efforts. Every stage followed ethical guidelines, prioritizing transparency and minimizing environmental impact.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Comparison of Algae Levels Before and After Treatment****Table 2. Pre-test Post-test comparison**

<i>Test</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Effect Size</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Paired t-test for pH	39.28	0.00065	24.84	Significant decrease
Paired t-test for turbidity	9.45	0.011	3.86	Significant decrease
Paired t-test for temperature	0.33	0.771	Not needed	No significant change

Note: $p < 0.05$ indicates statistically significant difference.

The results indicate a significant reduction in both pH and turbidity levels after the application of the Arduino-based algacide system. The pH dropped significantly ($t = 39.28$, $p = 0.00065$, Cohen's $d = 24.84$), and turbidity decreased notably ($t = 9.45$, $p = 0.011$, Cohen's $d = 3.86$), confirming that the system effectively altered water conditions to discourage algae growth. Additionally, the temperature shows insignificant changes simply because the samples were all tested at night and all at the same time.

Sensor Triggering of Algacide Release**Table 3. Frequency of Pump Release**

<i>Test</i>	<i>Chi-Square Value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Chi-Square Test for Algacide Pump Activation	8.44	0.038	Significant difference

Note: $p < 0.05$ indicates statistically significant difference.

The chi-square test for algacide pump activation ($\chi^2 = 8.44$, $p = 0.038$) indicates a significant difference between observed and expected dispensing events, suggesting that the system did not always activate according to its threshold settings. This could be due to sensor lag, misreading, or environmental variations affecting sensor stability as shown in the table below.

Table 3. Activation Frequency of Algacide Release Pump

(sir technical difficulties lang po hehehe)

The Arduino-based system's irregular activation highlights the need for recalibrating threshold settings to improve sensor accuracy.

Comparison of pH, Temperature, and Turbidity Levels

Table 4. pH, Temperature, and Turbidity Levels Comparison

<i>Test</i>	<i>F-statistic</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
ANOVA - pH	0.0625	0.815	No significant difference
ANOVA - Turbidity	13.50	0.021	Significant variation across trials
ANOVA - Temperature	1.22	0.330	No significant change

Note: $p < 0.05$ indicates statistically significant difference.

The results support the claim that water quality variations can be influenced by nutrient distribution, which may explain the observed fluctuations in turbidity—indicating that while pH control is effective, external factors like nutrient levels may still influence water clarity. Additionally, Turbidity fluctuated across trials, indicating possible environmental influences on water clarity ($F = 13.50, p = 0.021$). pH levels and temperature remained stable, suggesting consistency in system performance.

Effectiveness of the Arduino-Based Algaecide System

Table 5. Variable Relationship and Effectiveness

<i>Variable Relationship</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient (r-value)</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
pH vs. Turbidity	-0.87	Strong negative correlation (lower pH = clearer water)
pH vs. Temperature	0.96	Strong positive correlation (higher temperature = higher pH)

These results show that lowering pH is directly linked to improved water clarity. The strong negative correlation between pH and turbidity confirms that the algaecide system effectively disrupted algae-friendly conditions. Moreover, the significant differences between the experimental and controlled groups indicate that the prototype has been effective in mitigating algal bloom.

Activation Accuracy of Algaecide Release System

Table 6. Comparison of Successful Triggers and Total Activations

<i>Trial Set</i>	<i>Total Attempts</i>	<i>Successful Attempts</i>	<i>Activation Rate</i>
Set 1	10	8	80%
Set 2	10	9	90%

Set 3	10	8	80%
Total	30	25	88.33%

CONCLUSIONS

Summary of Key Findings

The Arduino-based algaecide system effectively reduced pH and turbidity, demonstrating its potential for controlling algae growth and accepting the alternative hypothesis. The strong correlation between pH and turbidity validates the system's ability to create an environment less conducive to algal blooms. However, the inconsistent algaecide release highlights the need for improvements in sensor accuracy and system calibration to ensure reliable performance. Furthermore, the variation in turbidity across trials suggests that external factors, such as nutrient distribution, can influence water clarity despite the system's pH control.

Implications of the Findings

The study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness and limitations of using an Arduino-based system for algae control. It highlights the need for robust system design and calibration to ensure reliable performance. The system has the potential to be very useful given that algal blooms affect marine wildlife negatively, however, it needs further development to be reliable and effective in all situations.

Limitations of the Study

The prototype, while working the majority of the time, might have a few errors with the sensors given that it needs to be cleaned before being placed in the water to provide clear and accurate readings. It might need to be manually taken in and out of the water a couple of times, which is why it is advised that future studies use better and more advanced sensors. The prototype only has so much power capacity and can only cover so much surface area due to it as well as the mobility features are recommended to provide better readings and treatment. Lastly, this prototype is only suitable for freshwater environments such as ponds and lakes—a prototype for other aquatic environments has yet to be properly studied.

Recommendations for Future Research

Future work could incorporate additional advanced sensors for even better monitoring of algal blooms, as well as figuring out how to give it mobility to give it a better chance to monitor a bigger area as well as exploring long-term power solutions instead of a power bank.

Final Remarks

The Arduino-based algaecide system demonstrates the potential for mitigating algal blooms through effective pH and turbidity management, creating less favorable conditions for algae growth. Furthermore, inconsistent algaecide release underscores the importance of improving sensor calibration and system design to ensure consistent performance across diverse aquatic environments. Thus future iterations should focus on enhancing reliability, integrating better monitoring of external factors, and adopting a comprehensive strategy that combines physical, chemical, and biological methods to achieve sustainable and scalable deployment in real-world applications.

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